

Production of enzymatic hydrolysates with *in vitro* antioxidant, antihypertensive, and antidiabetic properties from proteins derived from *Arthrospira platensis*

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Abstract

The microalga *Arthrospira platensis* BEA 005B was produced using 80 m² (9 m³) raceway photobioreactors achieving a biomass productivity of $326.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ g} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ ($28.2 \text{ g} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$) when operating the reactors in semi-continuous mode (0.33 day^{-1}). The produced biomass was rich in proteins ($58.1 \text{ g} \cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and carbohydrates ($25.6 \text{ g} \cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$); the content of phycocyanins and allophycocyanins was 115.4 and 36.9 mg·g⁻¹, respectively. Ultrasounds and high-pressure homogenisation allowed recovering approximately 90% of the initial protein content of the biomass; however, the energetic requirements of the former ($\sim 100 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$) were significantly lower than those of high-pressure homogenisation ($\sim 200 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$). An *in silico* analysis revealed that papain and ficin would allow releasing a large number of bioactive peptides with antioxidant, antihypertensive (ACE-I and renin), and antidiabetic (DPP-IV, α -amylase, and α -glucosidase) properties. Both were assessed *in vitro* together with Alcalase and pepsin leading to the generation of enzymatic hydrolysates with *in vitro* bioactivity.

Keywords: Microalgae, peptides, enzymatic hydrolysis, angiotensin-I, dipeptidyl peptidase-IV, diabetes, functional foods.

1. Introduction

Proteins have commercial interest not only as a source of amino acids but also because of their techno-functional properties and because they can be used as a source of hydrolysates and peptides with varied bioactivities. Bioactive peptides are short sequences of amino acids that impart a positive health effect to the consumer after being ingested. They are produced naturally from food proteins during the natural aging of foods or during their cooking or digestion (Toldrá, Gallego, Reig, Aristoy, & Mora, 2020). However, these processes are not controlled and the most widely studied strategy is enzymatic hydrolysis using commercial enzymes or enzyme mixtures. The research and commercial interest in peptides has increased significantly during the last two decades and some products have already achieved commercial success; for example, collagen-derived peptides are commercialised as skin protectors and joint-care products.

Bioactive peptides with *in vitro* activity have been generated from rice, chickpea, milk, cheese, meat, egg, soybean, and many other protein-containing foods (Daliri, Oh, & Lee, 2017). Spirulina is the commercial name given to the microalgae *Arthrospira platensis* and *Arthrospira maxima*. Despite being one of the natural resources with the highest protein content (55-65%), the number of Spirulina-derived bioactive peptides available in the literature is very low (Lafarga, Sánchez-Zurano, Villaró, Morillas-España, & Acien, 2021). Moreover, Spirulina is the most well-known microalga and consumers consider it a safe, sustainable, and nutritious ingredient (Lafarga, Rodríguez-Bermudez, Morillas-España, Villaró, García-Vaquero, Morán, Sánchez-Zurano, González-López, & Acien-Fernández, 2021). The most commonly described bioactivities were antioxidant properties and the potential to inhibit the activity of several enzymes

that are responsible for different health disorders. These include angiotensin-I (ACE-I; EC 3.4.15.1) and renin (EC 3.4.23.15), both enzymes linked to hypertension and other disorders related to metabolic syndrome, and dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV; EC 3.4.14.5), a serine protease that degrades and inactivates two incretin hormones that contribute to the enhancement of glucose-induced insulin secretion (Drucker, 2006). Bioactive peptides are also being studied as inhibitors of α -amylase (EC 3.2.1.1) and α -glucosidase (EC 3.2.1.20), responsible for the hydrolysis of dietary carbohydrates that are the major source of glucose in the blood (Apostolidis & Lee, 2010).

The present work had two major objectives. On the one side, the study aimed at producing the microalga *A. platensis* BEA 005B at a pre-commercial scale (80 m², 9 m³) and to assess the potential use of the biomass as a feedstock for protein isolation. Two different cell wall disruption technologies namely ultrasounds and high-pressure homogenisation were evaluated and the *Spirulina* proteins were recovered following an isoelectric solubilisation/precipitation strategy. On the other hand, the present work aimed at evaluating the potential use of the isolated proteins for being used as a source of enzymatic hydrolysates and peptides with *in vitro* antioxidant, antihypertensive, and/or antidiabetic properties. An *in silico* analysis was carried out before *in vitro* hydrolysis to identify the enzymes that would lead to the release of a larger number of known bioactive sequences.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Biomass production and characterisation

The microalga used was *A. platensis* BEA 005B provided by the Spanish Bank of Algae (Las Palmas, Spain). The microalgal biomass was produced using 80 m² (9 m³) raceway reactors at the SABANA Demonstration Plant (Almeria, Spain) in summer. The reactors were operated in semi-continuous mode with a depth of 0.10 m and a dilution rate of $3.82 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (0.33 day⁻¹). This means that 33% of the total volume of the culture was daily harvested and replaced with fresh culture medium. The culture medium was prepared using freshwater and commercial fertilisers: 0.90 kg·m⁻³ NaNO₃, 0.14 kg·m⁻³ KH₂PO₄, 0.18 kg·m⁻³ MgSO₄·7H₂O, 15 g·m⁻³ CaCl₂·2H₂O, 8.4 kg·m⁻³ NaHCO₃ and 30 g·m⁻³ of Karentol[®] (Konegard, Barcelona, Spain). The latter is an agricultural solid mixture of micronutrients that includes iron, copper, zinc, manganese, boron, and molybdenum. The pH was controlled at 9.8 ± 0.1 by on-demand injection of CO₂. Water evaporation was compensated by addition of freshwater. Once the steady state was achieved, the biomass was harvested by centrifugation and the fresh microalgal paste was frozen and stored at -20 °C until further use. The total protein, lipid, carbohydrate, and ash content of the biomass was calculated as described elsewhere (Ciardi, Gómez-Serrano, Morales-amaral, Acién, Lafarga, & Fernández-Sevilla, 2022). Biomass production was carried out simultaneously using three independent and identical photobioreactors and all the analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate per natural replicate.

2.2 Protein isolation

The fresh microalgal paste was suspended in tap water until a biomass concentration of 100 kg·m⁻³ and a final volume of $250 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$ (250 mL) prior to protein extraction. This concentration was selected based on unpublished experiments that demonstrated that this concentration could be achieved if the

reactors were harvested using ultrafiltration membranes instead of a centrifuge. The proteins were recovered following an isoelectric solubilisation/precipitation strategy based on a previous work (Sánchez-Zurano, Morillas-España, González-López, & Lafarga, 2020) but modifying the cell wall disruption step. The isolated proteins were frozen, freeze-dried using a Crydos-50 freeze-dryer (Telstar, Barcelona, Spain), and stored at 253 K (-20 °C) until further use. Different cell wall disruption strategies were evaluated. Sonication was carried out using a UP400S ultrasonic processor (Hielscher Ultrasound Technology, Teltow, Germany) operating at 400 W and 24 kHz. The probe was immersed 0.03 m into the culture, which was simultaneously stirred using a magnetic stirrer. The process duration varied from 30 to 120 s and the amplitude was fixed at either 50 or 100% to achieve specific energy consumption values in the range 10-200 kJ·kg⁻¹. The specific energy consumption of the sonication step was calculated as:

$$W = W_u \cdot t / m$$

where t is the duration of the step, m is the mass of the protein suspension, and W_u is the power input, which was either 200 or 400 W depending on the amplitude. In addition, high-pressure homogenisation was performed using a Panda Plus 2000 homogeniser (GEA Niro Soavi, Parma, Italy). The number of passes were varied between 1 and 3 passes and the homogenising pressure was varied from 10 to 100 MPa to achieve specific energy consumption values in the range 10-200 kJ·kg⁻¹. The specific energy consumption of the homogenisation step was calculated as:

$$W = P \cdot N_p / \rho$$

where P is the operating pressure, N_p is the number of passes, and ρ is the density of the suspension ($1,000 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$).

Following the laboratory-scale trials, the protein extraction step was up-scaled to a final volume of $2.5\cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$ (2.5 L). In this case, the cell wall of the microalgae was disrupted using the optimal conditions identified in the laboratory-scale trials. The other parameters and conditions were kept the same.

2.3 Enzymatic hydrolysis

Initially, an *in silico* analysis was carried out to identify the optimal enzyme to release bioactive peptides from *A. platensis*-derived proteins. The *in silico* strategy followed was reported elsewhere (Lafarga, O'Connor, & Hayes, 2014). Briefly, the amino acid sequence of *A. platensis*-derived proteins was accessed from the UniProt database at <http://www.uniprot.org/>. The cleavage sites of the enzymes pepsin, papain, thermolysin, and ficin were predicted using PeptideCutter, available at https://web.expasy.org/peptide_cutter/, and BIOPEP, available at <http://www.uwm.edu.pl/biochemia/index.php/en/biopep>. Following the *in silico* hydrolysis, BIOPEP was used to compare the generated peptides with bioactive sequences already reported and available in their database. The potential toxicity and allergenicity of the peptides generated *in silico* was estimated as described elsewhere (Lafarga, Wilm, Wynne, & Hayes, 2016).

The enzymes that were predicted to release a larger number of bioactive sequences were used *in vitro*. The isolated proteins were suspended in water at a concentration of $10 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and a final volume of $250\cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$ (250 mL). The hydrolysis was carried out using a controlled fermenter and the enzymes papain, ficin, pepsin, and Alcalase at an enzyme:protein ratio of 1:100 (w/w). The

agitation was kept constant at $3342.2 \text{ rad}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (350 rpm) and the temperature and the pH were set at the optimal for each enzyme: papain (338 K and 6.5), ficin (318 K and 7.0), pepsin (310 K and 2.5), and Alcalase (340 K and 8.2). The protein solution was preincubated for 600 s before the addition of the enzyme. The reaction was stopped after 5400, 10800, 16200, or 21600 s (90, 180, 270, or 360 min) of hydrolysis by heating the mixture at 365 K for 600 s and the pH was neutralised to pH 7.0 (O'Sullivan, Lafarga, Hayes, & O'Brien, 2017). The hydrolysates were centrifuged using a 3-18 KS centrifuge (Sigma Laborzentrifugen GmbH, Osterode am Harz, Germany) operating at $8,000 \times g$ for 600 s (10 min) and the supernatants were collected and freeze-dried.

The degree of hydrolysis (DH) was estimated using pH-stat technique following the equation:

$$DH = B \cdot N_B \cdot 1/\alpha \cdot 1/m_p \cdot 1/h_{tot} \cdot 100\%$$

Where B is the volume of base consumed (mL), N_B is the normality of the base, $1/\alpha$ is the average degree of dissociation of the α -amino groups related with the pK of the amino groups at the pH and temperatures used, m_p is the amount of protein in the reaction mixture (g), and h_{tot} is the sum of the millimoles of individual amino acids per gram of protein ($\text{meq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). The value of h_{tot} was estimated as 8 $\text{meq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and the values of $1/\alpha$ for each enzyme were calculated using a table available in a previous work (Toro & García-Carreño, 2003).

2.5 Assessment of bioactivity

The enzymatic hydrolysates were screened *in vitro* for antioxidant, antihypertensive, and antidiabetic properties. The antioxidant capacity of the extracts was assessed using the FRAP and DPPH methods as describes

elsewhere (Nicolau-Lapeña, Aguiló-Aguayo, Kramer, Abadías, Viñas, & Muranyi, 2021). The potential antihypertensive capacity was assessed through the *in vitro* ACE-I and renin inhibitory capacity. Both were determined following methodologies described elsewhere (Lafarga, Rai, O'Connor, & Hayes, 2016). Captopril and Aliskiren were used as positive controls at a concentration of $1 \text{ g} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ ($1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$). The potential antidiabetic properties were assessed through the capacity of the extracts to inhibit the enzymes DPP-IV, α -amylase, and α -glucosidase. The DPP-IV inhibitory capacity was assessed as described in a previous work (Lafarga, Rai, O'Connor, & Hayes, 2016). The tripeptide IPI at a concentration of $1 \text{ g} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ ($1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) was used as the control. The α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory capacity was assessed as described elsewhere (Apostolidis & Lee, 2010) using a 5111 9100 Multiskan FC microplate reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain). The inhibitory activity of the hydrolysates was expressed as percentage of inhibition; the IC_{50} value of the hydrolysates with the highest bioactivity was calculated as the concentration needed to inhibit the activity of the enzymes by 50%.

2.6 Statistical analysis

The results are expressed as mean values \pm standard deviations. The data were analysed using analysis of variance with the software Statgraphics 18 (Statgraphics Technologies Inc., USA). A Tukeys' HSD procedure was used to identify where the sample differences occurred.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Biomass production and protein isolation

Fig. 1A shows the biomass concentration in the raceway reactors during biomass production. The temperature of the culture during the biomass production was on average 301.5 ± 1.2 K (28.4 ± 1.2 °C) and showed maximum and minimum values of 303.2 and 300.5 K, respectively (30.1 and 27.4, respectively). The biomass productivity achieved was $326.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ g·m⁻²·s⁻¹ (28.2 ± 1.7 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹), which is higher than that reported in a previous work in the same region but using a different microalga (Morillas-España, Lafarga, Gómez-Serrano, Ación-Fernández, González-López, 2020). Only a limited number of studies evaluated the productivity of *A. platensis* at a pilot-scale using photobioreactors located outdoors. The biomass productivity achieved in pilot-scale reactors located in Brazil was on average $250 \cdot 10^{-6}$ g·m⁻²·s⁻¹ or 21.6 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ (Morais, Radmann, Andrade, Teixeira, Bruschi, & Costa, 2009), demonstrating the potential commercial production of Spirulina in the south of Spain. Further works will evaluate the productivity of the selected strain during the other seasons, as the present work was carried out in summer where the environmental conditions are best suited for producing this microalga. The quantum yield of the culture during the semi-continuous production ranged between 0.55 and 0.60, suggesting that the culture was not subjected to any stress condition. This parameter decreases when the culture is subjected to either a lack of nutrients, an excess of light, or is in contact with heavy metals or toxins that affect microalgal growth (Ciardi, Gómez-Serrano, Morales-Amaral, Ación, Lafarga, & Fernández-Sevilla, 2022).

The composition of the produced biomass is shown in Table 1. Spirulina is widely known for its high protein content, which was 58.1 g·100 g⁻¹ on a dry weight basis. Indeed, most of the Spirulina-containing foods are marketed as “rich in proteins”. In the present study, the protein content of the biomass was comparable to that

observed in previous works (Gómez, Guzmán-Carrasco, Lafarga, & Acién-Fernández, 2021; Rosa, Moraes, Cardias, Souza, & Costa, 2015; Taragjini, Ciardi, Musari, Villaró, Morillas-España, Alarcón, & Lafarga, 2022) and to that of commercial Spirulina powders available at the USDA FoodData Central database (<https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/>). Spirulina is not only used in the food industry because of its high protein content but also as a food colourant because of its high concentration of pigments (Lafarga, Sánchez-Zurano, Villaró, Morillas-España, & Acién, 2021). The most common pigments present in microalgal biomass are carotenoids and chlorophylls; however, cyanobacteria including Spirulina are especially rich in phycobiliproteins. Phycobiliproteins are especially interesting food ingredients because they are water-soluble and have a potent antioxidant capacity. Spirulina is especially rich in C-phycoyanin, a blue-coloured photosynthetic pigment with nutraceutical properties and a market value that ranges from 140 to 1400 €·kg⁻¹ (Shanthi, Premalatha, & Anantharaman, 2021). This molecule was used as a source of bioactive peptides with *in vitro* antidiabetic properties (Li, Aiello, Bollati, Bartolomei, Arnoldi, & Lammi, 2020). In the present study, the phycocyanin content of the produced biomass was estimated as 115 mg·g⁻¹, which was slightly higher than that of *A. platensis* LEB 52 produced in 0.45 m³ photobioreactors (Silveira, Burkert, Costa, Burkert, Kalil, 2007). The commercial Spirulina powder had a lower phycocyanin concentration. It is known that the content of C-phycoyanin can be strongly affected by light availability during microalgae production, suggesting that the commercial biomass was produced in deeper cultures (the higher the culture depth, the lower the light availability because of the self-shading effect of microalgae).

One of the main challenges of utilising microalgae as a source of proteins and other valuable molecules is the rigid cell wall of microalgae, which renders the use of a cell wall disruption step mandatory. Many studies evaluated the efficacy of physical, chemical, and biological cell wall disruption strategies and results so far suggested that the disruption step needs to be designed for each process independently as the cell wall of different microalgal strains varies significantly (Alhattab, Kermanshahi-Pour, & Brooks, 2019). The cell wall of *A. platensis* consist of four layers, two of them rich in fibrillary molecular, a peptidoglycan-rich layer, and a β -1,2-glucan layer (Chen, Xu, Yu, Yuan, Kong, sun, Wang, Zhuang, Zhang, & Guo, 2020). Despite not being as resistant as the cell wall of other eukaryotic microalgae, a cell wall disruption step when extracting proteins from *A. platensis* is mandatory to achieve high recovery yields (Sánchez-Zurano, Morillas-España, González-López, & Lafarga, 2020). Fig. 2A shows the effect of ultrasound processing and high-pressure homogenisation on the protein recovery yields. Both technologies allowed recovering over $55 \text{ g} \cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$, which suggests a protein recovery of almost 90%. Indeed, 87.8 or 91.0% of the initial protein content was recovered when the biomass was disrupted using ultrasounds or high-pressure homogenisation, respectively. The main difference between these results was the energy required to achieve the maximum extraction yields, 2-fold higher when using the high-pressure homogenisation. For this reason, ultrasounds were selected as the optimal technology from those investigated and were used for the extraction of proteins at a larger scale. When the biomass was not pre-treated, the protein recovery yields were on average $35.1 \pm 2.3 \text{ g} \cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$, demonstrating that both technologies led to protein recoveries that were at least 55% higher. The ultrasound-assisted protein extraction was up-scaled to a final

volume of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$, achieving a protein recovery yield of $53.6 \pm 1.9 \text{ g} \cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$, which was comparable to that achieved using $250 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$ (250 mL) fermenters. Future studies will further upscale the process and assess protein recovery yields using industrial fermenters and centrifuges.

3.2 *In silico* analysis and enzymatic hydrolysis

There are several animal- and plant-derived enzymes commercially available as well as enzymes derived from microbial sources. For this reason, an *in silico* analysis was carried out to predict which enzymes would release a larger number of known bioactive peptides. A total of 27 proteins, including phycocyanin and allophycocyanin, were studied; all of them demonstrated to be excellent sources of bioactive peptides with antioxidant capacity and ACE-I, renin, and DPP-IV inhibitory properties. Overall, the enzymes that were predicted to release the larger number of ACE-I inhibitory peptides were papain (366) and ficin (300). For example, the di-peptide IL, which was described as an inhibitor of ACE-I in a previous work (Wu, Aluko, & Nakai, 2006), was predicted to be released from the β -subunit of C-phycocyanin after cleavage using papain. Both enzymes were also the most efficient releasing DPP-IV inhibitory peptides with 530 and 413 DPP-IV inhibitory sequences released by papain and ficin, respectively. For example, the di-peptide AG, which was reported to inhibit the enzyme DPP-IV (Lan, Ito, Ohno, Motoyama, Ito, & Kawarasaki, 2015) was predicted to be released from the α -chain of allophycocyanin. The peptide WR, which was shown to have the highest DPP-IV inhibitory capacity among di-peptides (Lan Ito, Ohno, Motoyama, Ito, & Kawarasaki, 2015) was also generated *in silico* from phytoene synthase using papain. Ficin and papain were predicted to be the best enzymes for generating antioxidant sequences (55) and renin-inhibitory sequences (22), respectively. All

the peptides generated *in silico* were predicted to be non-toxic; however, some of the peptides were potentially allergenic based on *in silico* results. Although the route of sensitisation is not yet known, consumption of Spirulina can cause allergic reactions (it is uncommon but possible). Allergenicity risk assessment as well as potential cross reactivity with other allergens have been suggested as necessary (Le, Knulst, & Röckmann, 2014). Based on the *in silico* results, the enzymes that showed higher potential for releasing bioactive sequences from Spirulina proteins were papain and ficin; both were assessed *in vitro* together with Alcalase and pepsin.

The yield and degree of hydrolysis achieved using the different enzymes are shown in Fig. 2B. The DH refers to the proportion of cleaved peptide bonds in a protein hydrolysate; a higher DH means that a larger amount of peptide bonds was cleaved and therefore, the average molecular weight of the peptides is smaller. The DH is relevant because the activity of a given peptide depends on its amino acid sequence (length and order). Overall, the enzyme that allowed achieving the highest DH was Alcalase, which is consistent with previous reports (Purschke, Meinlschmidt, Horn, Rieder, & Jäger, 2018). A similar DH was achieved when using the enzymes papain and ficin; however, because of the different specificity of these two enzymes, the generated hydrolysates had a different peptide composition. Papain is a cysteine hydrolase with a fairly broad specificity that cleaves on peptide bonds that involve positively charged amino acids such as arginine, lysine, and residues following phenylalanine (Vatić, Mirković, Milošević, Jovčić, & Polović, 2020). In turn, the data available today suggests a quite unspecific activity of ficin with a certain preference for aromatic amino acids such as tyrosine, phenylalanine, and tryptophan (Morellon-Sterling,

El-Siar, Tavano, Berenguer-Murcia, & Fernández-Lafunte, 2020). Pepsin led to the lowest DH, which rapidly increased to approximately 5% during the first 5400 s (90 min) and reached 7% after 21600 s (360 min) of hydrolysis. Most of the bioactive peptides reported to date are short sequences of 2-10 amino acids in length. However, the bioactivity of the hydrolysates generated using pepsin is especially interesting as it is one of the main enzymes in the digestive system of humans and its use can give an idea of the potential release of peptides upon consumption – although a more complete simulation of digestion such as the INFOGEST protocol (Brodkorb et al., 2019) is necessary to predict the release of peptides upon consumption. The DH could be potentially increased by including into the process a pre-treatment such as sonication or high pressure processing (Thoresen, Álvarez, Vaka, Rustad, Sone, & Fernández, 2020), and further studies will assess their potential to increase the DH or the bioactivity of the generated hydrolysates.

3.3 Assessment of *in vitro* bioactivity

The antioxidant capacity was determined using the DPPH and FRAP methods. The main advantages and drawbacks of these methods have been summarised elsewhere (Amorati & Valgimigli, 2015). Both give an indication of the radical-trapping activity or the reducing ability of the microalgal extracts. This means that they do not measure antioxidant capacity directly but indirectly based on the reaction of the antioxidant and a synthetic coloured radical (DPPH) or another oxidising agent that is Fe³⁺ (FRAP). The antioxidant capacity of the produced enzymatic hydrolysates is shown in Fig. 3. Enzymatic hydrolysis led to a higher antioxidant capacity ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that bioactive peptides with antioxidant capacity were released from the isolated proteins. The observed increase was

especially high when using pepsin (DPPH) and ficin (FRAP); the latter was suggested as the best-suited enzymes to release antioxidant peptides *in silico*. When the hydrolysates were produced using pepsin and Alcalase, higher antioxidant activities were observed at longer hydrolysis durations. In turn, when the hydrolysates were produced using ficin or papain the highest antioxidant capacity was observed after 5400 s (90 min) of hydrolysis ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that a higher DH led to the cleavage of some antioxidant peptides generated during the first 5400 s (90 min) and to the loss of bioactivity.

The *in vitro* antihypertensive activity of the enzymatic hydrolysates produced is shown in Fig. 4. It was estimated by means of the potential of the hydrolysates to inhibit the activity of the enzymes ACE-I and renin. Both involved in the development of hypertension and other health disorders involved in the metabolic syndrome (Eckel, Grundy, & Zimmet, 2005). Papain was suggested *in silico* as the optimal enzyme to release known bioactive sequences from Spirulina, which is consistent with previous *in silico* studies (Lafarga, O'Connor, Hayes, 2014). The hydrolysates produced *in vitro* using papain and Alcalase demonstrated the highest ACE-I inhibitory activity, inhibiting the enzymes' activity by approximately 100% (after 16200 s or 270 min of hydrolysis using Alcalase and 21600 s or 360 min of hydrolysis using papain). Most of the ACE-I inhibitory peptides identified to date are di- or tri-peptides and it was expected that the higher the DH the higher the ACE-I inhibitory activity. Two of the most widely studied and used ACE-I inhibitory peptides, IPP and LPP, are tri-peptides and long hydrolysis times (24-72 h) are needed to maximise their concentration during hydrolysis (Stressler, Eisele, & Fischer, 2013). The IC_{50} value of the two enzymatic hydrolysates with the highest activity was 0.56 ± 0.03 and 0.49 ± 0.05 g·m⁻³ for the enzymatic

hydrolysate generated using papain during 21600 s (360 min) or Alcalase during 16200 s (270 min), respectively. These values are comparable to those obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis of wheat gluten using Alcalase and Protamex (0.38-0.42 g·m⁻³) (Zhang, Chang, Liu, Li, Yan, & Jiag, 2020) and those obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis of spent brewers' yeast using an extract derived from *Cyanara cardunculus* (0.14-0.64 g·m⁻³) (Amorim, Pinheiro, & Pintado, 2019). Previous works identified peptides with ACE-I inhibitory activity; for example, the peptide IRDLDYY with an IC₅₀ value of 1.7 mM (Anekthanakul, Senachak, Hongsthong, Charoonratana, & Ruengjitchatchawalyaet, 2019), or the peptides VTY and LGVP with IC₅₀ values of 23.4 and 45.7 μM that were detected after hydrolysis of Spirulina proteins using thermolysin (Zhang, Li, Zhang, Li, Zhu, & Yan, 2022). Renin is the rate-limiting step of the antihypertensive cascade in most species; its inhibition is a therapeutic goal because of the substrate specificity of this enzyme when compared to ACE-I (Ames, Atkins, & Pitt, 2019). The capacity of the generated hydrolysates to inhibit renin is shown in Fig. 4. Overall, the percentage of inhibition was lower than that of ACE-I, which can be mainly attributed to the above-mentioned higher specificity of renin. The highest inhibitory capacity was determined after hydrolysis using Alcalase during 16200 s (270 min). The IC₅₀ value of this hydrolysate was 0.85 ± 0.09 g·m⁻³.

Furthermore, Fig. 5 shows the capacity of the generated hydrolysates to inhibit the enzyme DPP-IV. The inhibition of DPP-IV is now one of the main strategies to control the development of diabetes; these molecules enhance glucagon-like peptide-1 preservation and expansion of β-cell mass improving blood glucose control. Recent findings also indicated that inhibitors of DPP-IV could reduce glycaemic variability in type-2 diabetes patients (Lee, Lee, Kim, & Kim, 2019). In

the present work, both the protease used and the hydrolysis time had a significant effect on the DPP-IV inhibitory activity of the hydrolysates ($p < 0.05$). Overall, the capacity of the enzymatic extracts to inhibit DPP-IV was lower when compared to ACE-I. DPP-IV inhibitory peptides are generally short sequences of 2-5 amino acids in length. Therefore, higher hydrolysis times led to higher DPP-IV inhibitory activity, which is in line with previous works (Nongonierma, Cadamuro, Le Gouic, Mudgil, Maqsood, & FitzGerald, 2019). The hydrolysates produced using Alcalase during 16220 and 21600 s (270 and 360 min) showed the highest DPP-IV inhibitory capacity (~47%), which was comparable to that obtained for hydrolysates produced from milk or quinoa (Nongonierma, Le Maux, Dubrulle, Barre, & FitzGerald, 2015; Nongonierma, Cadamuro, Le Gouic, Mudgil, Maqsood, & FitzGerald, 2019). Other *Arthrospira* strains have been evaluated as sources of bioactive peptides with DPP-IV inhibitory activity. For example, a recent work reported a DPP-IV IC_{50} value of $3.4 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ after hydrolysis using pepsin (Aiello, Boschini, Bollati, Arnoldi, & Lammi, 2019) and another obtained IC_{50} values of $\sim 3.8\text{-}5.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ after hydrolysis using pepsin, trypsin, Alcalase, or bromelain (Liu, Bai, & Fu, 2022). In this second work, only phycobiliproteins derived from *Spirulina* were used and not all the protein fraction. The α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory capacity of the hydrolysates was lower when compared to that of the other enzymes studied ($p < 0.05$). A slight increase in the observed bioactivity was detected at higher hydrolysis times; however, the inhibitory potential of the hydrolysates was below 15% independently of the enzyme used or the duration of the reaction (data not shown).

Overall, the results demonstrated that the isolated proteins contained bioactive sequences that could be released from their parent proteins *in vitro* using different

enzymes. The *in vitro* hydrolysis of the proteins is not related with the proteolysis that occurs during gastrointestinal digestion, this means that the generated hydrolysates should be incorporated into foods as an ingredient. The bioactivity of these added ingredients should be first resistant to the food processing or preparation stage. Temperature, for example, might reduce the bioactivity of enzymatic hydrolysates. This needs to be investigated for each peptide independently, as previous works revealed that although proteins and peptides are thermolabile materials, bioactive peptides can resist large temperature variations (Reunanen & Saris, 2004). Moreover, the peptides released during the present study might be further hydrolysed during gastrointestinal digestion. Poor stability of peptides to gastrointestinal degradation is limiting their use as functional food ingredients; strategies including encapsulation are being investigated and have been effectively increased the oral bioavailability of peptides (Sridhar, Inbaraj, & Chen, 2021). ADME studies (absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion) are now an essential part of the lead optimisation for synthetic molecules, including bioactive peptides (Shou, 2020).

4. Conclusions

The present work demonstrated the potential of up scaling the production of the microalga *Arthrospira platensis* BEA 005B and its use as a protein feedstock for bioactive peptide generation. The protein content of the biomass was higher than that of other protein sources such as dairy products, legumes, or meat and the bioactivity of the enzymatic hydrolysates was in line with those reported for other foods. Both, ultrasounds and high-pressure homogenisation are efficient technologies that allow recovering a large percentage of the proteins produced

by *A. platensis*. However, the former led to the highest recovery yield with a significantly lower energy input. The isolated proteins were hydrolysed using different enzymes including papain, pepsin, ficin, and Alcalase. The generated hydrolysates showed a high antioxidant capacity and the potential to inhibit the activity of the enzymes ACE-I, renin, and DPP-IV. The inhibitory capacity of the enzymes α -amylase and α -glucosidase was more limited at the concentrations studied in this work. Future studies will identify the peptides that are responsible for the observed bioactivity and further scale up the hydrolysis process.

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Conflict of interests

Authors declare no conflict of interests.

Data availability

The data related with the biomass production is available at the SABANA database (<http://sabana.ual.es/>). The data related with protein isolation and hydrolysis is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

CRedit contributor roles

S. Villaró: Investigation, formal analysis, writing – original draft; **S. Jiménez-Márquez:** Investigation; **E. Musari:** Investigation; **R. Bermejo:** Resources; and **T. Lafarga:** Formal analysis, supervision, writing – review & editing, funding acquisition.

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Figure captions

Fig. 1. Biomass productivity. The biomass production was carried out in summer in semi-continuous mode at a fixed dilution rate of 0.33 day^{-1} .

Fig. 2. (A) Effect of cell wall disruption on the protein recovery yields and (B) degree of hydrolysis achieved using different enzymes

Fig. 3. Antioxidant capacity of the enzymatic hydrolysates produced using (A) pepsin, (B) papain, (C) ficin and (D) Alcalase. The samples were assessed at a concentration of $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ ($1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). Different letters indicate statistical differences.

Fig. 4. Angiotensin-I-converting enzyme and renin inhibitory activity of the enzymatic hydrolysates produced using (A) pepsin, (B) papain, (C) ficin and (D) Alcalase. The samples were assessed at a concentration of $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ ($1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). Different letters indicate statistical differences.

Fig. 5. Dipeptidyl peptidase-IV inhibitory activity of the enzymatic hydrolysates produced using pepsin, papain, ficin and Alcalase. The samples were assessed at a concentration of $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ ($1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). Different capital letters indicate statistical differences between hydrolysis times. Different lower case letters indicate significant differences between enzymes.

Tables

Table 1. Composition of *A. platensis* BEA 005B